

GENERALIZATION OF PÓLYA-SZEGÖ TYPES INEQUALITIES INVOLVING K-ATANGANA BALEANU FRACTIONAL INTEGRAL OPERATOR

AVINASH V. KAWARAKHE*, P. S. AVHALE AND VISHAL B. MAGAR

ABSTRACT. The main objective of this paper is to establish some new fractional integral inequalities of Pólya-Szegő type by using k-Atangana Baleanu fractional integral. Our finding demonstrate the effectiveness of k-Atangana Baleanu fractional integrals in extending classical inequalities.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fractional calculus is widely recognized as a comprehensive generalization of classical calculus, wherein the concepts of differentiation and integration are extended to non-integer (arbitrary) orders. Initially conceived as a purely theoretical mathematical construct, fractional calculus has evolved into a powerful analytical framework with applications spanning numerous scientific and engineering domains, including but not limited to mechanics, physics, biology, chemistry, electrochemistry, and bioengineering (see [8, 14, 15, 21]). The advancement of fractional calculus theory has given rise to a wide range of fractional operators, which have been the subject of extensive investigation in the literature, including studies such as the Riemann–Liouville [19, 29], Caputo [2, 37], Hilfer [16], Erdélyi–Kober [4], Hadamard [20], and ψ -fractional derivatives and integrals [5], each characterized by unique mathematical formulations and properties. Furthermore, the continuous development of new fractional operators often distinguished by the choice of kernel within the integral operator has led to an increasingly diverse and comprehensive set of definitions (see [6, 13, 17, 32] and references therein).

Among these recent developments, Atangana and Baleanu [9], have introduced one more dimension to the study of fractional calculus by presenting a fractional integral and derivative operators through non-singular, non-local kernel based on the Mittag-Leffler function known as AB-fractional operators. As described by Atangana and Baleanu, this operator addresses several key issues present in the classical formulations and enables improved modeling of real-world systems. To further generalize the AB approach, Kermausuor and Nwaeze [18], proposed the k-Atangana–Baleanu fractional integral, which combines the structure of the Atangana–Baleanu operator with the flexibility of the k-Gamma function. The

2020 *Mathematics Subject Classification.* 26A33, 26D10, 26D15.

Key words and phrases. Pólya-Szegő types inequalities, k-Atangana Baleanu fractional integral, integral inequality.

PÓLYA-SZEGÖ INEQUALITY

k-Atangana–Baleanu fractional integral operator retains the non-locality and non-singularity of the AB operator while offering a broader framework that includes many classical operators as special cases.

A wide variety of such operators led researchers to use them, however some authors studied fractional differential problems and some established fractional integral inequalities for these operators. For instance, Ntyouas et al. [23], established Chebyshev type integral inequalities using Hadamards fractional operators. Rashid et al. [27, 28] proposed a new class of generalized proportional fractional integral operators with respect to another function and established associated Grüss-type and reverse Minkowski-type inequalities. Yewale and Pachpatte [34], presented Minkowski, Hölder and Hardy type inequalities by employing ψ -Riemann Liouville fractional integral operators. Budak and Pehlivan [10], obtained Ostrowski, trapezoid and midpoint type inequalities by considering Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. Many researchers have established a variety of inequalities by employing various fractional operators and their generalizations (see [22, 30, 35, 36]) and references therein.

In 1925, Pólya and Szegő proved the following important inequality (see [26]):

$$\frac{\int_a^b \zeta^2(s) ds \int_a^b \eta^2(s) ds}{\left(\int_a^b \zeta(s)\eta(s) ds\right)^2} \leq \frac{1}{4} \left(\sqrt{\frac{mn}{MN}} + \sqrt{\frac{MN}{mn}} \right)^2. \quad (1.1)$$

In 2013, Anber and Dahmani [7], provided fractional version of (1.1) by using Riemann-Liouville fractional integral as follows:

Let ζ and η be two integrable function on $[a, b]$ such that $0 < m \leq \zeta(s) \leq M < \infty$, $0 < m \leq \eta(s) \leq M < \infty$, then

$$\frac{{}^{\text{AB}}\mathfrak{J}_a^\alpha \zeta^2(s) {}^{\text{AB}}\mathfrak{J}_a^\alpha \eta^2(s)}{{}^{\text{AB}}\mathfrak{J}_a^\alpha \zeta(s) {}^{\text{AB}}\mathfrak{J}_a^\alpha \eta(s)} \leq \frac{1}{4} \left(\sqrt{\frac{mn}{MN}} + \sqrt{\frac{MN}{mn}} \right)^2.$$

In recent decades, Pólya and Szegő inequality has attracted widespread attention and has been thoroughly studied and extended in several directions. Ntyouas et al. [24] obtained Pólya and Szegő inequality by using Riemann-Liouville fractional integral. Set et al. [31] established Pólya–Szegő type inequalities by employing the generalized Katugampola fractional integral. These results were subsequently utilized to establish new forms of fractional Chebyshev inequalities. Nisar et al. [25] established some fractional Chebyshev–Pólya–Szegő-type integral inequalities by considering the generalized weighted fractional integral containing another function in the kernel. In recent study, significant contribution have been made to which Pólya and Szegő inequality leads and numerous extensions and improvements can be found related to it in the literature [3, 11, 12, 33].

Motivated by above, the present work aims to establish new Pólya–Szegő-type integral inequalities using the k-Atangana–Baleanu fractional integral operator. By leveraging the generality of the k-Gamma function and the regularizing effect of the Mittag-Leffler kernel, this approach enables the derivation of more robust fractional inequalities that encompass a wider class of function behaviors. The new

PÓLYA-SZEGÖ INEQUALITY

inequalities presented here extend existing results in fractional calculus. We organize the paper as follows: In section 2, we give some preliminaries and definitions which used throughout this work. In section 3, we prove our main results on Pòlya-Szegö type inequalities using k-Atangana Baleanu fractional integral. Concluding remark given in the last section.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Now in this section we give some preliminaries and definitions required for our subsequent discussions.

Definition 1 [9] Let $0 < \alpha < 1$. Then the left Atangana–Baleanu fractional integral operator of a real valued function ρ is defined as

$${}^{AB}\mathfrak{J}_a^\alpha \rho(z) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)}\rho(z) + \frac{\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-t)^{\alpha-1} \rho(t) dt, \quad z > a,$$

where $\mathbb{B}(\alpha) > 0$ such that $\mathbb{B}(0) = \mathbb{B}(1) = 1$.

Definition 2 [1] Let $0 < \alpha < 1$. Then the right sided Atangana–Baleanu fractional integral operator of a real valued function ρ is defined as

$${}^{AB}\mathfrak{J}_b^\alpha \rho(z) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)}\rho(z) + \frac{\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_z^b (t-z)^{\alpha-1} \rho(t) dt, \quad z < b,$$

where $\mathbb{B}(\alpha) > 0$ such that $\mathbb{B}(0) = \mathbb{B}(1) = 1$.

Definition 3 [18] Let $\alpha > 0$ and $k > 0$. Then the left and right sided k-Atangana–Baleanu fractional integral operators of a real valued function ρ are defined as

$${}^{AB}_k\mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha \rho(z) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)}\rho(z) + \frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-t)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \rho(t) dt, \quad z > a,$$

and

$${}^{AB}_k\mathfrak{J}_{b-}^\alpha \rho(z) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)}\rho(z) + \frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_z^b (t-z)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \rho(t) dt, \quad z < b,$$

where $\mathbb{B}(\alpha) > 0$ such that $\mathbb{B}(0) = \mathbb{B}(1) = 1$ and

$$\Gamma_k(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\frac{t^k}{k}} dt.$$

In present paper we use only left sided k-Atangan-Baleanu fractional integral operator to carry out our results.

For $\rho(z) = 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{AB}_k\mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha (1) &= \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} + \frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-t)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} dt \\ &= \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} + \frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \frac{k}{\alpha} (z-a)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \end{aligned}$$

PÓLYA-SZEGÖ INEQUALITY

$$= \frac{1 - \alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} + \frac{(z - a)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}}{\mathbb{B}\Gamma_k(\alpha)}.$$

3. PÓLYA-SZEGÖ TYPE INEQUALITY

In this section, we establish Pólya-Szegő type inequality using k-Atangana Baleanu fractional integral operator.

Theorem 3.1. Let $\alpha > 0$ and $k > 0$. Let $\zeta, \eta, u_1, u_2, v_1, v_2$ be positive integrable functions on $[0, \infty)$ satisfying

$$0 < u_1(s) \leq \zeta(s) \leq u_2(s), \quad 0 < v_1(s) \leq \eta(s) \leq v_2(s) \quad (s \in [a, z], z > a \geq 0). \quad (3.1)$$

Then following inequality holds:

$$\frac{({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha v_1 v_2 \zeta^2)(z) ({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha u_1 u_2 \eta^2)(z)}{[({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha (u_1 v_1 + u_2 v_2) \zeta \eta)(z)]^2} \leq \frac{1}{4}. \quad (3.2)$$

Proof. From (3.1) we have

$$\left(\frac{u_2(s)}{v_1(s)} - \frac{\zeta(s)}{\eta(s)} \right) \geq 0. \quad (3.3)$$

Also,

$$\left(\frac{\zeta(s)}{\eta(s)} - \frac{u_1(s)}{v_2(s)} \right) \geq 0. \quad (3.4)$$

Taking multiplication between (3.3) and (3.4), we have

$$\left(\frac{u_2(s)}{v_1(s)} - \frac{\zeta(s)}{\eta(s)} \right) \left(\frac{\zeta(s)}{\eta(s)} - \frac{u_1(s)}{v_2(s)} \right) \geq 0.$$

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & (u_1(s)v_1(s) + u_2(s)v_2(s))\zeta(s)\eta(s) \\ & \geq v_1(s)v_2(s)\zeta^2(s) + u_1(s)u_2(s)\eta^2(s). \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

Multiplying both the side of inequality (3.5) by $\frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)}(z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1}$ and integrating with respect to s from a to z , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} (u_1(s)v_1(s) + u_2(s)v_2(s))\zeta(s)\eta(s) ds \\ & \geq \frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} v_1(s)v_2(s)\zeta^2(s) ds \\ & \quad + \frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} u_1(s)u_2(s)\eta^2(s) ds. \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

Again multiplying both the side of inequality (3.5) by $\frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)}$ and replacing s by z , we get

$$\frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} (u_1(z)v_1(z) + u_2(z)v_2(z))\zeta(z)\eta(z)$$

PÓLYA-SZEGÖ INEQUALITY

$$\geq \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} v_1(z)v_2(z)\zeta^2(z) + \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} u_1(z)u_2(z)\eta^2(z). \quad (3.7)$$

Adding (3.6) and (3.7), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} (u_1(z)v_1(z) + u_2(z)v_2(z))\zeta(z)\eta(z) \\ & + \frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} (u_1(s)v_1(s) + u_2(s)v_2(s))\zeta(s)\eta(s) ds \\ & \geq \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} v_1(z)v_2(z)\zeta^2(z) + \frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} v_1(s)v_2(s)\zeta^2(s) ds \\ & + \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} u_1(z)u_2(z)\eta^2(z) + \frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} u_1(s)u_2(s)\eta^2(s) ds. \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha (u_1v_1 + u_2v_2)\zeta\eta)(z) \\ & \geq ({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha v_1v_2\zeta^2)(z) + ({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha u_1u_2\eta^2)(z). \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

By using AM-GM inequality to the right hand side of (3.9) i.e. $p+q \geq 2\sqrt{pq}$, for $p, q \in \mathbb{R}^+$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha v_1v_2\zeta^2)(z) + ({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha u_1u_2\eta^2)(z) \\ & \geq 2\sqrt{({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha v_1v_2\zeta^2)(z)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha u_1u_2\eta^2)(z)}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

From (3.6) and (3.7), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha (u_1v_1 + u_2v_2)\zeta\eta)(z) \\ & \geq 2\sqrt{({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha v_1v_2\zeta^2)(z)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha u_1u_2\eta^2)(z)}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

Squaring on both the sides of inequality (3.11), we get required inequality (3.2). \square

Corollary 3.1. Let $\alpha > 0$ and $k > 0$. Let ζ and η be positive integrable functions on $[0, \infty)$. Then, for the real constants m, n, M, N , if the following conditions:

$$0 < m \leq f(s) \leq M < \infty, \quad 0 < n \leq g(s) \leq N < \infty, \quad (s \in [a, z], t > a \geq 0). \quad (3.12)$$

hold, then the following inequality also holds:

$$\frac{({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha \zeta^2)(z)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha \eta^2)(z)}{[({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha \zeta\eta)(z)]^2} \leq \frac{1}{4} \left(\sqrt{\frac{mn}{MN}} + \sqrt{\frac{MN}{mn}} \right)^2. \quad (3.13)$$

Remark 3.1. For $k = 1$, we get Pólya-Szegö type inequality (3.2) for AB fractional integral.

PÓLYA-SZEGÖ INEQUALITY

Theorem 3.2. Let $\alpha > 0$, $\beta > 0$ and $k > 0$. Let $\zeta, \eta, u_1, u_2, v_1, v_2$ be positive integrable functions on $[0, \infty)$ satisfying the conditions (3.1). Then following inequality holds:

$$\frac{({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha u_1 u_2)(z)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\beta v_1 v_2)(z)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha \zeta^2)(z)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\beta \eta^2)(z)}{[({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha u_1 \zeta)(z)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\beta v_1 \eta)(z) + ({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha u_2 \zeta)(z)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\beta v_2 \eta)(z)]^2} \leq \frac{1}{4}. \quad (3.14)$$

Proof. From the condition (3.1), for $s, r \in [a, z]$, $z > a \geq 0$, we obtain

$$\left(\frac{u_2(s)}{v_1(r)} - \frac{\zeta(s)}{\eta(r)} \right) \geq 0, \quad (3.15)$$

and

$$\left(\frac{\zeta(s)}{\eta(r)} - \frac{u_1(s)}{v_2(r)} \right) \geq 0. \quad (3.16)$$

Taking multiplication between (3.14) and (3.16), we get

$$\left(\frac{u_1(s)}{v_2(r)} + \frac{u_2(s)}{v_1(r)} \right) \frac{\zeta(s)}{\eta(r)} \geq \frac{\zeta^2(s)}{\eta^2(r)} + \frac{u_1(s)u_2(s)}{v_1(r)v_2(r)} \quad (3.17)$$

Multiplying both the sides of (3.17) by $v_1(r)v_2(r)\eta^2(r)$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & u_1(s)\zeta(s)v_1(r)\eta(r) + u_2(s)\zeta(s)v_2(r)\eta(r) \\ & \geq v_1(r)v_2(r)\zeta^2(s) + u_1(s)u_2(s)\eta^2(r). \end{aligned} \quad (3.18)$$

Now, on both sides of (3.18), taking multiplication by $\frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)}(z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1}$ and integrating with respect to s from a to z , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & v_1(r)\eta(r)\frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} u_1(s)\zeta(s) ds \\ & + v_2(r)\eta(r)\frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} u_2(s)\zeta(s) ds \\ & \geq v_1(r)v_2(r)\frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \zeta^2(s) ds \\ & + \eta^2(r)\frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} u_1(s)u_2(s) ds. \end{aligned} \quad (3.19)$$

Multiplying both the side of inequality (3.18) by $\frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)}$ and replacing s by z , we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} u_1(z)\zeta(z)v_1(r)\eta(r) + \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} u_2(z)\zeta(z)v_2(r)\eta(r) \\ & \geq \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} v_1(r)v_2(r)\zeta^2(z) + \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} u_1(z)u_2(z)\eta^2(r). \end{aligned} \quad (3.20)$$

Adding (3.19) and (3.20), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & v_1(r)\eta(r)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha u_1 \zeta)(z) + \eta(r)v_2(r)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha u_2 \zeta)(z) \\ & \geq v_1(r)v_2(r)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha \zeta^2)(z) + \eta^2(r)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^\alpha u_1 u_2)(z). \end{aligned} \quad (3.21)$$

PÓLYA-SZEGÖ INEQUALITY

Now, on both sides of (3.21), taking multiplication by $\frac{\beta}{k\mathbb{B}(\beta)\Gamma_k(\beta)}(z-r)^{\frac{\beta}{k}-1}$ and integrating with respect to r from a to z , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} u_1 \zeta)(z) \frac{\beta}{k\mathbb{B}(\beta)\Gamma_k(\beta)} \int_a^z (z-r)^{\frac{\beta}{k}-1} v_1(r) \eta(r) dr \\ & + ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} u_2 \zeta)(z) \frac{\beta}{k\mathbb{B}(\beta)\Gamma_k(\beta)} \int_a^z (z-r)^{\frac{\beta}{k}-1} v_2(r) \eta(r) dr \\ \geq & ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} \zeta^2)(z) \frac{\beta}{k\mathbb{B}(\beta)\Gamma_k(\beta)} \int_a^z (z-r)^{\frac{\beta}{k}-1} v_1(r) v_2(r) dr \\ & + ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} u_1 u_2)(z) \frac{\beta}{k\mathbb{B}(\beta)\Gamma_k(\beta)} \int_a^z (z-r)^{\frac{\beta}{k}-1} \eta^2(r) dr. \end{aligned} \quad (3.22)$$

Multiplying both the side of inequality (3.21) by $\frac{1-\beta}{\mathbb{B}(\beta)}$ and replacing r by z , we get

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} u_1 \zeta)(z) \frac{1-\beta}{\mathbb{B}(\beta)} v_1(z) \eta(z) + ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} u_2 \zeta)(z) \frac{1-\beta}{\mathbb{B}(\beta)} \eta(z) v_2(z) \\ \geq & ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} \zeta^2)(z) \frac{1-\beta}{\mathbb{B}(\beta)} v_1(z) v_2(z) + ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} u_1 u_2)(z) \frac{1-\beta}{\mathbb{B}(\beta)} \eta^2(z). \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

Adding (3.22) and (3.23), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} u_1 \zeta)(z) ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} v_1 \eta)(z) + ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} u_2 \zeta)(z) ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} v_2 \eta)(z) \\ \geq & ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} \zeta^2)(z) ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} v_1 v_2)(z) + ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} u_1 u_2)(z) ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} \eta^2)(z). \end{aligned} \quad (3.24)$$

By using AM-GM inequality to the right hand side of (3.24) i.e. $a+b \geq 2\sqrt{ab}$, for $a, b \in \mathbb{R}^+$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} u_1 \zeta)(z) ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} v_1 \eta)(z) + ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} u_2 \zeta)(z) ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} v_2 \eta)(z) \\ \geq & 2\sqrt{({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} \zeta^2)(z) ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} v_1 v_2)(z) ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} u_1 u_2)(z) ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} \eta^2)(z)}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.25)$$

Squaring both the sides of (3.25), we get required inequality (3.13). \square

Corollary 3.2. Let $\alpha > 0$, $\beta > 0$ and $k > 0$. Let ζ and η be positive integrable functions on $[0, \infty)$ satisfying the condition (3.12), then following inequality holds:

$$\frac{({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} 1) ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} 1) ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} \zeta^2)(z) ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} \eta^2)(z)}{[({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} \zeta)(t) ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} \eta)(z)]^2} \leq \frac{1}{4} \left(\sqrt{\frac{mn}{MN}} + \sqrt{\frac{MN}{mn}} \right)^2, \quad (3.26)$$

where

$${}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} (1) := \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} + \frac{(z-a)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \quad \text{and} \quad {}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} (1) := \frac{1-\beta}{\mathbb{B}(\beta)} + \frac{(z-a)^{\frac{\beta}{k}}}{\mathbb{B}(\beta)\Gamma_k(\beta)}.$$

Remark 3.2. For $k = 1$, we get Pólya-Szegö type inequality (3.14) for Atangana-Baleanu fractional integral.

PÓLYA-SZEGÖ INEQUALITY

Theorem 3.3. Let $\alpha > 0$, $\beta > 0$ and $k > 0$. Let $\zeta, \eta, u_1, u_2, v_1, v_2$ be positive integrable functions on $[0, \infty)$ satisfying the conditions (3.1). Then following inequality holds:

$$({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} \zeta^2)(z)({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} \eta^2)(z) \leq ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} \frac{u_2 \zeta \eta}{v_1})(z)({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} \frac{v_2 \zeta \eta}{u_1})(z). \quad (3.27)$$

Proof. From the condition (3.1), for $s \in [a, z]$, $z > a$, we have

$$\zeta^2(s)v_1(s) \leq u_2(s)\zeta(s)\eta(s),$$

it follows that

$$\zeta^2(s) \leq \frac{u_2(s)\zeta(s)\eta(s)}{v_1(s)}. \quad (3.28)$$

Multiplying both the side of inequality (3.28) by $\frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)}(z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1}$ and integrating with respect to s from a to z , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \zeta^2(s) ds \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha}{k\mathbb{B}(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^z (z-s)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \frac{u_2(s)\zeta(s)\eta(s)}{v_1(s)} ds. \end{aligned} \quad (3.29)$$

Multiplying both the side of inequality (3.28) by $\frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)}$ and replacing s by z , we get

$$\frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} \zeta^2(z) \leq \frac{1-\alpha}{\mathbb{B}(\alpha)} \frac{u_2(z)\zeta(z)\eta(z)}{v_1(z)}. \quad (3.30)$$

Adding (3.29) and (3.30), we have

$${}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} \zeta^2(z) \leq ({}^{AB} \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} \frac{u_2 \zeta \eta}{v_1})(z). \quad (3.31)$$

Again using the condition (3.1), for $r \in [a, z]$, $z > a$, we have

$$\eta^2(r) \leq \frac{v_2(r)\zeta(r)\eta(r)}{u_1(r)}. \quad (3.32)$$

Multiplying both the side of inequality (3.32) by $\frac{\beta}{k\mathbb{B}(\beta)\Gamma_k(\beta)}(z-s)^{\frac{\beta}{k}-1}$ and integrating with respect to r , from a to z , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\beta}{k\mathbb{B}(\beta)\Gamma_k(\beta)} \int_a^z (z-r)^{\frac{\beta}{k}-1} \eta^2(r) dr \\ & \leq \frac{\beta}{k\mathbb{B}(\beta)\Gamma_k(\beta)} \int_a^z (z-r)^{\frac{\beta}{k}-1} \frac{v_2(r)\zeta(r)\eta(r)}{u_1(r)} dr. \end{aligned} \quad (3.33)$$

Multiplying both the side of inequality (3.32) by $\frac{1-\beta}{\mathbb{B}(\beta)}$ and replacing r by z , we get

$$\frac{1-\beta}{\mathbb{B}(\beta)} \eta^2(z) \leq \frac{1-\beta}{\mathbb{B}(\beta)} \frac{v_2(z)\zeta(z)\eta(z)}{u_1(z)}. \quad (3.34)$$

PÓLYA-SZEGÖ INEQUALITY

Adding (3.33) and (3.34), we obtain

$${}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} \eta^2(z) \leq \left({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} \frac{v_2 \zeta \eta}{u_1} \right)(z). \quad (3.35)$$

Taking multiplication between (3.31) and (3.32), we get required inequality (3.27). \square

Corollary 3.3. Let $\alpha > 0$, $\beta > 0$ and $k > 0$. Let ζ and η be positive integrable functions on $[0, \infty)$ satisfying the condition (3.12), then the following inequality holds:

$$\frac{({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} \zeta^2)(z)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} \eta^2)(z)}{({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\alpha} \zeta \eta)(z)({}^{AB}_k \mathfrak{J}_{a+}^{\beta} \zeta \eta)(t)} \leq \frac{MN}{mn}. \quad (3.36)$$

Remark 3.1. For $k = 1$, we get Pólya-Szegő type inequality (3.27) for AB fractional integral.

4. CONCLUSION

The generalization of Pólya-Szegő type inequalities utilizing the k-Atangana-Baleanu fractional integral operator represents a significant advancement in the field of fractional calculus. The novel framework established herein extends the classical results to a broader class of functions, thereby enriching the theoretical understanding of fractional inequalities. By incorporating the k-Atangana-Baleanu operator, we have demonstrated the potential of fractional integrals to refine and generalize existing inequalities, offering a more robust toolkit for dealing with various functional forms. In this paper, we obtained some Pólya-Szegő-type inequalities by employing k-Atangana Baleanu fractional integral operators. The main objective of this paper is to contribute to a greater extent of studies within the theory of mathematical inequalities.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Abdeljawad and D. Baleanu, Integration by parts and its applications of a new local fractional derivative with Mittag-Leffler nonsingular kernel, *J. Nonlinear Sci. Appl.*, 10, pp. 1098–1107, 2017.
- [2] R. Agarwal, S. Hristova, D. O'Regan, A survey of Lyapunov functions, stability and impulsive Caputo fractional differential equations, *Fract. Calc. Appl. Anal.*, 19, pp. 290–318, 2016.
- [3] A. Ahmad and M. Anwar, Refinements of Pólya-Szegő and Chebyshev type inequalities via different fractional integral operators, *Helvion*, 10(15), pp. 1-12, 2024.
- [4] B. Al-Saqabi B and V. S. Kiryakova, Explicit solutions of fractional integral and differential equations involving Erdelyi-Kober operators, *Appl. Math. Comput.*, 95(1), pp. 1–13, 1998.
- [5] R. Almeida, A Caputo fractional derivative of a function with respect to another function, *Commun. Nonlinear Sci. Numer. Simul.*, 44, pp. 460–481, 2017.
- [6] R. Almeida, Fractional differential equations with mixed boundary conditions, *Bull. Malays. Math. Sci. Soc.*, 42(4), pp. 1687–1697, 2019.
- [7] A. Anber, Z. Dahmani, New integral results using Pólya-Szegő inequality, *Acta Comment. Univ. Tartu. Math.*, 17(2), pp. 171–178, 2013.

PÓLYA-SZEGÖ INEQUALITY

- [8] T. M. Atanackovic, S. Pilipovic S, B. Stankovic and D. Zorica, Fractional calculus with applications in mechanics: wave propagation, impact and variational principles, *Wiley, London*, 2014.
- [9] A. Atangana and D. Baleanu, New fractional derivatives with nonlocal and non-singular kernel: Theory and application to heat transfer model, *Ther. Sci.*, 20, 2016.
- [10] H. Budak and E. Pehlivan, Weighted Ostrowski, trapezoid and midpoint type inequalities for Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, *AIMS Mathematics*, 5(3), pp. 1960–1984, 2020.
- [11] S. I. Butt, A. O. Akdemir, M. Y. Bhatti, M. Nadeem, New refinements of Chebyshev–Pólya–Szegő-type inequalities via generalized fractional integral operators, 2020, *J. Inequal. Appl.*, Art. no. 157, 2020.
- [12] E. Deniz, A. O. Akdemir, E. YüKsel, New extensions of Chebyshev–Pólya–Szegő type inequalities via conformable integrals, *AIMS Math.*, 5(2), pp. 956–965, 2020.
- [13] R. Garra, R. Gorenflo, F. Polito F and Z. Tomovski Z, Hilfer–Prabhakar derivatives and some applications, *Appl. Math. Comput.*, 242, pp. 576–589, 2014.
- [14] L. Gaul, P. Klein, S. Kempfle, Damping description involving fractional operators, *Mech. Systems Signal Processing*, 5(2), pp. 81–88, 1991.
- [15] W. G. Glockle and T. F. Nonnenmacher, A fractional calculus approach of self-similar protein dynamics, *Biophys J.*, 68(1), pp. 46–53, 1995.
- [16] R. Hilfer, Applications of Fractional Calculus in Physics, *World Scientific, Singapore*, 2000.
- [17] U. N. Katugampola, New fractional integral unifying six existing fractional integrals, *arXiv preprint arXiv:1612.08596*, 2016.
- [18] S. Kermausuor and E. R. Nwaeze, New Fractional Integral Inequalities via k-Atangana–Baleanu fractional integral operators, *fractal fract.*, 7(10), pp. 1-13, 2023.
- [19] A. A. Kilbas, H. M. Srivastava, J. J. Trujillo, Theory and applications of fractional differential equations, *Elsevier, Amsterdam*, vol. 204, 2006.
- [20] M. Li and J. Wang, Existence of local and global solutions for Hadamard fractional differential equations, *Electron. J. Differ. Equ.*, 2015(166), pp. 1–8, 2015.
- [21] R. L. Magin, Fractional calculus in bioengineering, *Danbury: Begell House Inc. Publisher*, 2006.
- [22] I. Mumcu I., E. Set, A. Kashuri, Chebyshev type inequalities involving generalized proportional fractional integral operators, *Transyl. J. Math. Mechanics*, 12(1), pp. 27–35, 2020.
- [23] S. K. Ntouyas, S. D. Purohit, J. Tariboon, Certain Chebyshev type integral inequalities involving Hadamards fractional operators, *Abstr. Appl. Anal.*, Art. ID 249091, pp. 1-7, 2014.
- [24] S. K. Ntouyas, P. Agarwal, J. Tariboon, On Pólya–Szegő and Chebyshev types inequalities involving the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral operators, *J. Math. Inequal.*, 10(2), pp. 491–504, 2016.
- [25] K. S. Nisar, G. Rahman, D. Baleanu, M. Samraiz, S. Iqbal, On the weighted fractional Pólya–Szegő and Chebyshev-types integral inequalities concerning another function, *Adv. Differ. Equ.*, Art. no. 623, 2020.
- [26] G. Pólya and G. Szegő, Problems and Theorems in Analysis, *Translated from the German; original version: Julius Springer Berlin 1925; Springer: New York, NY, USA; Berlin, Germany*, Vol. I, 1972.
- [27] S. Rashid, F. Jarad, M. A. Noor, H. Kalsoom, Y. M. Chu, Inequalities by means of generalized proportional fractional integral operators with respect to another function, *Mathematics*, 7(12), 2020.
- [28] S. Rashid, F. Jarad, Y. M. Chu, A note on reverse Minkowski inequality via generalized proportional fractional integral operator with respect to another function, *Math. Probl. Eng.*, Art. Id. 7630260, pp. 1-12, 2020.
- [29] S. G. Samko, A. A. Kilbas and O. I. Marichev, Fractional Integrals and Derivatives, Theory and Applications, *Gordon and Breach, Yverdon*, 1993.

PÓLYA-SZEGÖ INEQUALITY

- [30] M. Z. Sarikaya, Z. Dahmani, M. E. Kiris, F. Ahmad, (k, s) -Riemann-Liouville fractional integral and applications, *Hacet. J. Math. Stat.*, 45(1), pp. 77-89, 2016.
- [31] E. Set, Z. Dahmani, I. Mumcu, New extensions of Chebyshev type inequalities using generalized Katugampola integrals via Pólya-Szegő inequality, *Int. J. Optim. Control. Theor. Appl.*, 8(2), pp. 137-144, 2018
- [32] J. V. Sousa and E. C. de Oliveira, On the ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative, *Commun. Nonlinear Sci. Numer.*, 60, pp. 72-91, 2018.
- [33] W. Yang, Certain new weighted Young and Polya Szego-type inequalities for unified fractional integral operators via an extended generalized Mittag-Leffler function with applications, *Fractals*, 30(6), 2250106, 2022.
- [34] B. R. Yewale and D. B. Pachpatte, On Some reverses of Minkowski's, Hölder's and Hardy's type inequalities using ψ -fractional integral operators, *SEAJMMS*, 18(1), pp. 97-112, 2022.
- [35] B. R. Yewale, D. B. Pachpatte, Tariq A. Aljaaidi, Chebyshev types inequalities involving (k, ψ) -proportional fractional integral operators, *J. Funct. Spaces.*, 2022, Art. ID 3966177, pp. 1-6, 2022.
- [36] B. R. Yewale and D. B. Pachpatte, Some new Chebyshev type inequalities via Extended generalized fractional integral operator, *J. Fract. Calc. Appl.*, 12(2), pp. 11-19, 2021.
- [37] Y. Xu, Fractional boundary value problems with integral and anti-periodic boundary conditions, *Bull. Malays. Math. Sci. Soc.*, 39, pp. 571-587, 2016.

AVINASH V. KAWARAKHE

DEPT. OF MATHEMATICS, SHRI SHIVAJI ART'S, COMMERCE AND SCIENCE COLLEGE, KANNAD, CHH. SAMBHAJINAGAR, MAHARASHTRA 431103, INDIA.

Email address: avinashkawarkhe77@gmail.com

P. S. AVHALE

DEPT. OF MATHEMATICS, SHRI SHIVAJI ART'S, COMMERCE AND SCIENCE COLLEGE, KANNAD, CHH. SAMBHAJINAGAR, MAHARASHTRA 431103, INDIA.

Email address: avhaleps@yahoo.com

VISHAL B. MAGAR

DEPT. OF MATHEMATICS, SHRI SHIVAJI ART'S, COMMERCE AND SCIENCE COLLEGE, KANNAD, CHH. SAMBHAJINAGAR, MAHARASHTRA 431103, INDIA.

Email address: vishalmagar111@gmail.com